

UNIVERSITY OF CAGLIARI

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

The mechanisms put in place by Italian legislation¹ to combat harassment and promote equal opportunities in public workplaces, including academia, have seen their role slightly strengthened. Some universities and research organisations have also shared experiences in addressing the issue. The requirement to introduce Codes of Conduct that specifically refer to sexual harassment and to setting up a protection system involving the Guarantee Committee of Equal Opportunities (CUG)² and the confidential counsellor³ has helped to increase awareness of gender-based violence (GBV) and has ushered in concrete tools to fight the phenomenon. However, the lack of specific guidelines on how to draw up a Code of Conduct and to implement it in practice, without any independent body with control and coordinate functions, has resulted in a highly differentiated system of protection (Perini 2019). Another weakness has been the tendency to focus on the issue of gender equality rather than on GBV, minimising the gender component in addressing issues such as sexual harassment and gender discrimination. This has produced a formalised and technical approach and reduced the overall effectiveness of the system. Even though most Italian universities have introduced Codes of Conduct regarding harassment, there has never been any formal action taken against universities that have not yet complied with the national legislation, despite the fact that the Italian law provides for the possibility of sanctioning organisations that fail to do so. It is hard to estimate how many higher education institutions and research funding organisations in Italy have failed to comply with national regulations, since there is no specific body that can gather such data at the national level. As of December 2020, only 32 of 85 universities had instituted the position of a confidential counsellor within their protection system.⁴

¹ Legislative Decree No. 198/2006, Code of Equal Opportunities in the Workplace.

² A formal body with proposing, consulting, and verification functions for the development of a culture of equal opportunities and against discrimination.

³ The confidential counsellor helps victims of discrimination and harassment and, at the request of the person concerned, takes on the case and informs them of the most suitable way of dealing with it.

⁴ <https://www.visir.is/g/20171884043d>

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The main policies of the University of Cagliari are general policies that address GBV but are not dedicated solely to this issue. These are the Gender Equality Plan of the University of Cagliari (2020)⁵ and the Code of Ethics and Conduct – Single Act (2019),⁶ with the University CUG as the main actor. The university offices in charge of defining internal disciplinary sanctions and warnings in the event of sexual discrimination and gender-based harassment or violence are the Ethics Commission and the Disciplinary Board. The process of ascertaining facts, depending on their gravity, is, however, only a preparatory phase before involving the appropriate protection bodies in the event that the case constitutes a crime (specifically contacting the relevant police department). Both the Psychological Counselling channel aimed at students and the Student Supervisor (Garante degli Studenti) can act as the first points for reporting incidents, though no paths are currently set up specifically for such cases. Finally, the teaching evaluation forms of the university's teachers, which students are required to fill in at the end of a course, contain a special section where students can anonymously report the details of incidents of this type, which are then assessed by the Ethics Commission, with a view to determining whether a disciplinary process is necessary.

However, the procedures that have been developed for dealing with sexual harassment⁷ are yet to be implemented and need to be made more friendly, and no one has yet been appointed to the position of confidential counsellor (although its introduction is envisioned in the new Plan for Positive Actions valid for the three-year period of 2022-2024). A monitoring system for cases of harassment and discrimination needs to be developed. In the Gender Equality Plan, there is a section about preventing and managing cases of sexual harassment, with a stated aim to revise the University Code of Conduct to incorporate a gender perspective on sexual harassment in the workplace and to create a handbook outlining an updated procedure for dealing with harassment.⁸

Since 2017, at the impetus of students' associations, various initiatives against GBV have been introduced. This includes the screening – in collaboration with the CUG – of a **video⁹ the university made** on the topic at the start of each academic year. Since 2017, **an information campaign called '25 November All Year Long: Against Gender Violence'¹⁰** has been conducted annually, and lectures, seminars, and workshops aimed at prevention are organised by the CUG throughout the academic year.

Another initiative was the creation of an **information point**, where staff from the Police's Crime Division, the Mobile Squad, and psychologists from local anti-violence centres, made themselves available to provide information and support to victims. The event took place on 14 February 2020, and it was aimed at all students and staff. The event was promoted on the university website.¹¹

⁵ Università di Cagliari. (2020). Piano di uguaglianza di genere dell'Università degli studi di Cagliari.

⁶ Università di Cagliari. (2019) Codice etico e di comportamento - Codice unico.

⁷ This is clearly described by the expert opinion of Ester Cois: "both the Psychological Counselling channel aimed at students as well as the figure of the Student Guarantor can act as the very first reporting points for episodes of harassment, without however currently setting up paths specifically dedicated to these cases".

⁸ The definition of the vademecum will begin in the autumn of 2021, with the collaboration of the CUG and the Office of the Delegate for gender equality, in view of the establishment of a specific commission on these issues to be formalised by 2024, according to the expert opinion of Ester Cois.

⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1yI3aF11lol&t=8s>

¹⁰ 25 novembre tutto l'anno. Contro la violenza di genere.

¹¹ https://www.unica.it/unica/page/it/universita_e_polizia_assieme_contro_la_violenza_di_genere

In November 2021 the Faculty of Engineering and Architecture launched the competition 'A Thought to Erase Gender-Based Violence', to accompany the project 'A Brushstroke to Erase Gender-Based Violence', as part of which a bench in the forecourt of the Engineering Campus was painted red by dozens of people – including students, teachers, and technical-administrative staff – as a symbolic and permanent act of powerful testimony against GBV. The competition invited the student population of UniCa to identify a quote that significantly symbolises the awareness campaign against gender-based violence, the aim being to select one quote and have it engraved on a plaque near the bench in the faculty garden.

URLs

- › Gender Equality Plan:
<https://unicapress.unica.it/index.php/unicapress/catalog/view/978-88-3312-021-8/17/312-2>
- › Code of Ethics and Conduct:
https://trasparenza.unica.it/files/2019/03/Codice_adottato_DR.pdf

Entry into force: The plan defines different actions to be taken in different years from 2021 to 2024 and 2029, respectively.

TRAINING

Not addressed in the report.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

The university offers a master's degree in gender equality.¹²

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: Sexual harassment is addressed in both documents.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

¹² Although the degree is primarily focused on the theme of gender equality, however, starting from the 2016/2017 program, it is also possible to find topics related to GBV: criminology and gender victimology (15 h lesson); operating methodologies of anti-violence centres (7.5 h lesson).
<https://unica.it/unica/protected/16519/0/def/ref/AVS16515/>

7Ps covered: 5Ps are covered – prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution and policy.

The Gender Equality Plan refers to prevalence and prevention. Both of the policies refer to protection. The Code of Ethics and Conduct also covers prosecution and policy.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Intersectionality addressed

No

Specific vulnerable groups

Not defined

Target groups

Both policies cover academic staff, non-academic staff, and students.

Bystanders addressed: No.

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: Yes. Protection: A handbook is to be drawn up for reporting sexual harassment and discriminatory behaviours by 2022. A working group on the subject is to be set up. The Code of Ethics and Conduct is to be adapted (formal actions are required).

Monitoring: No.

Evaluation: No.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

Yes. It is described in the Code of Ethics and Conduct.

The policy defines: who to contact.

Student vs staff: who to contact.

Who to contact: Students refer for their reporting to the Student Supervisor (Garante degli studenti), while university staff (technical and teachers) report to the head of the structure to which they belong or to the person who presides over and/or coordinates the activity.

Staff vs staff: who to contact.

Who to contact: There is specific information about managers involved in harassment cases as perpetrators: If a reported incident involves a manager, the communication must be addressed to the general manager. If the reported incident concerns the general manager, a department director, the chair of the Faculty Council, the director of the centre, or a head of the structure, the communication must be addressed to the rector. If the report concerns the rector, the communication must be addressed to the dean.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Karla Nicole Brunello in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

